

An Assessment of Housing Quality in India: A Spatio-Comparative Analysis of Major Social Groups

Dr. Sahab Deen Rawat, Assistant Professor, School of Humanities, Lovely Professional University, Phagwara, Punjab

Abstract

The housing quality along with the availability of household basic facilities and amenities plays an important role in shaping the healthy, safe and comfortable household environment to a prosperous life for the family members. Traditional society is characterized by noticeable distinction among the various social groups. In general, lower castes in Indian society is considered one of the most backward social groups in term of housing quality and availability of basic facilities and amenities in comparison to other advantaged social groups, especially to Upper Castes (UC) having the privilege of good quality of housing and basic facilities and amenities. The present study is an attempt to present an assessment of housing quality and condition of basic amenities through a spatial-comparative analysis between two major social groups i.e. upper-caste and scheduled castes in India. This study is primarily based on the quantitative exercise of primary data interviewed with a set of the schedule of structured questionnaires sampled from a field survey of eight major states across India. A principal component analysis (PCA) score has been designed from different selected housing and amenities' variables in order to assess the spatio-comparative statuses of the household and, plotted on the map by using geospatial technology from the geographical point of view. Analysis of housing quality and availability of basic facilities and amenities for both the social groups divulges that there is a large spatial variation in the level of housing quality and basic facilities and amenities across selected states in India. The spatial assessment of housing quality and basic facilities and amenities shows a similar pattern for both the social groups. However, Scheduled castes' households are deprived of housing quality and in the availability of personal household amenities and facilities in comparison to their counterparts of the privileged social group across India.

Keywords: *Basic-Amenities, Household-Facility, Housing-Quality, India, Lower-Castes, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Scheduled Castes (SC), Spatial-Variation, Spatio-Comparative, and Upper-Castes.*

Introduction

The socio-economic factors highly influence the progress of an individual member as well as a whole society. In the context of Indian society, the factors like gender, caste, class, religion, and region are important in determining factors access the prosperity of wealth, basic facilities and amenities in order to achieve a socio-economic status in the society. Indian society has been described as a “compartmentalized” society. Indian society has a large number of social, ethnic, religious, occupational and economic groups that uphold distinct and dissimilar lifestyles. The hierarchical social system by which these groups are related and reciprocally accommodated is so complex as to challenge general explanation (Galanter, 1984). Thus, there is conspicuous dissimilarity in Indian society based on caste, class, gender, and region across the Indian society. Moreover, there are numerous constraining traditional as well as customary laws prevailing in the society that direct and determine the mode of production activities and occupation in order to achieve socio-economic prosperity in society. Accordingly, various socioeconomic factors play a significant role in access and achieve socioeconomic basic facilities, amenities, and prosperity in society. Resultantly, the socio-economic backgrounds of the Scheduled Castes are inferior in nature (Aikara, 1980). Most of the problems confronted by the Scheduled Castes have their origins in their prolonged backwardness and isolation due to their caste status. An underlying factor that makes these problems very prominent is their relatively poor background (Dreze, and Kingdon, 1999). Historically, lower castes and women have found at the bottom-level place in Indian society. The socio-economic backwardness of

Scheduled Castes is the function of their traditionally lower position in the social hierarchy (Chauhan, 1975). Thus, they remain at the bottom level in the hierarchal society and are deprived of access to socio-economic prosperity. Therefore, the present research article presents an assessment of housing quality and availability of basic household facilities and amenities through a spatio-comparative analysis between two major social groups of upper-caste and scheduled castes. The present study is based on primary household data interviewed from villages in the study areas. A composite index from different social-economic variables has been developed through the PCA score for particular districts in order to analyze the spatial variation between two social groups i.e. upper-caste and scheduled castes. The paper can be divided into three major sections i.e. housing quality, availability of basic facilities and amenities and discussion in order to fulfill the objective of the study.

Data Source and Methodology

The present article is based on primary household data interviewed from villages of eight states across India. There was a total of 603 samples interviewed with a schedule of structured questionnaires from 40 villages of eight states in India. For the assessment of housing quality and availability of household basic amenities and facilities, a composite index of different selected variables has been created through the computation of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) score for the particular districts in order to analyze the spatial variation for both the social groups across the surveyed states in India. The principal component analysis is the methodology of index development that deals with the technique that merged a number of variables into one or a few components or indicators. Thus, constructed index characterizes similar as possible with respect to all the indicators or component features that were synthesized into one or a few components (Abdi & Williams, 2010). Besides, PCA is a multivariate procedure for scrutinizing a

data set in which observations are demarcated by several inter-correlated quantitative dependent variables. Thus, PCA pools a large number of indicators into a few conceptual components containing the characteristics of all the combined indicators (Jolliffe, 1986). Computer package SPSS 21 enablesto computation abilityof Principal Component Analysis scores for a given distribution (NUEPA, 2009).

Table-1: Properties of PCA Composite Index										
Scheduled Castes (SC)										
SL	PCA Index	Variables	KMO =0.6 Min.	BTS= p<0.05	CC = > 0.3 % & many	Eigen value = > 1	Scree Plot	Cmpnt. Explains	Cmpnt. Extracted	Rotation Solution
1	HQI	6	0.782	0.000	Many	1	1	70.549	First	Varimax
2	HBAI	13	0.650	0.000	Many	4	>1	37.397	First	Varimax
Upper-Castes (Non-Reserved)										
SL	PCA Index	Variables	KMO =0.6 Min.	BTS= p<0.05	CC= > 0.3 % many	Eigen Value = > 1	Scree Plot	Cmpnt. Explains	Cmpnt. Extracted	Rotation Solution
1	HQI	6	0.743	0.000	Many	5	1	71.220	First	Varimax
2	HBAI	13	0.492	0.000	Many	1	1	37.277	First	Varimax

Note: **HQI**=Housing Quality Index, **HBAI**=Household Basic Amenities Index

There are 603 household samples that have been utilized for analysis. This makes 40 different cases. So, 40 cases (N=40) with the different number of variables for separate PCA index have been mention in table 1. In this way, PCA composite indices have been createdfor fulfilling the essential conditions of Principal Component Analysis as stated in the above table 1.

Results

Housing Quality

Housing quality, material resources, and learning resources are uniquely related to the per capita incomeare directly related to the social and economic achievementand education (Robert H. Bradley and Diane L. Putnick, 2012).Poor housing quality and inadequate access to material resources affects directly to health and immunity of children and restrict what parents can do

to protect children and promote their development (Bartlett, 1999). Thus, Housing quality determines the health, social and economic status of an individual. A composite index of PCA score of 6 variables i.e. semi-pucca house, pucca house, cemented floor, cemented wall, cemented roof, and good condition house has been computed to express the housing quality across the surveyed districts. The spatial pattern of housing quality is showing with a choropleth map plotted by composite index (*Housing Quality Index-HQI*) in the Map-1 and 2.

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

Housing Quality of Scheduled Castes' Household

The housing quality of Scheduled Caste households reveals that 48% of the total Scheduled Caste houses were semi-pucca, and 29% were the pucca house. The Scheduled Castes' household having cemented floor, cemented wall and cemented roof records 31%, 39% and 33% of the total households respectively. However, only 20% of the total households were found in good and living conditions for Scheduled Castes (Appendix-1).

The map-1 of the housing quality of Scheduled Caste families shows an asymmetrical pattern across India. The housing quality of Scheduled Castes' households indicates that the district Sitapur has recorded the highest HQI score with 2.51 followed by Bijpur and Bikaner. On the other hand, district Karimnagar (-1.82) stands at the bottom level of housing quality preceded by Kannur and Ernakulam. Map 1 shows that the overall housing qualities of Scheduled Castes households in the Northern states are far better than Southern states. In these states, 10 districts such as Ajmer, Bijpur and Purulia, etc. come under High-level housing quality, and 7 districts like Udaipur, Murshidabad, etc. record medium level housing quality and, only 3 districts i.e. Barmer, Gorakhpur, etc. register low level of HQI score among the Scheduled castes households. On the contrary, none of the districts records high-level housing quality, in Southern states for Scheduled Castes. However, 8 districts like Pune, Karwar, and SPS Nellore, etc. recorded medium level and another 12 districts like Kannur, Vishakhapatnam, etc. have recorded a low level of HQI index for Scheduled Castes population.

Housing Quality of Upper-Castes' Household

The housing qualities of upper-caste households show that there are only 9% of the total houses are semi-pucca in nature, and 90% are pucca houses. The Upper-Castes' household having cemented floor, cemented wall and

cemented roof shares 92%, 91% and 82% of the total correspondingly. There are 82% of the total upper-castes households have shown in good living conditions (Appendix-2).

The housing quality index of Upper-Castes' households shows that the district Ernakulam has recorded the highest HQI score with 0.70 followed by Alappuzha and Mallapuram; on the other hand, Sitapur (-3.05) stand at bottom level preceded by Barmer and Araria. Map 2 indicates that the upper-castes' households having good housing quality across the surveyed area with few exceptions. There is a total of 28 districts like Ernakulam, Bikaner, Karwar, etc. have recorded a high level and, 7 districts like Sonbhadra, Visakhapatnam, and Anantapur registered medium level, and remaining 5 districts like Barmer, Araria, etc. have recorded low level of HQI score.

Household Basic Amenities

Access to high quality housing materials, safe drinking water, improved sanitation, and a separate kitchen with closed stove could be secure to young children by avoiding diseases like malnutrition, diarrhea and serious respiratory illnesses and injuries (Fisk, Lei-Gomez & Mendell, 2007) which are most important aspect to provide a healthy and clean home environment for their children progress. A PCA score has computed by utilizing 13 variable of household basic amenities i.e. electricity, electric meter, 12-18 hours power supply, 18 hours power supply, hand pump, tap water, water facility inside the home, personal source of water facility, use of LPG for cooking, separate kitchen, sanitary toilet facility without flush, sanitary toilet facility with flush and sewer connection with toilet facility. The composite index of the PCA score (*Household Basic Amenity Index (HBAI)*) has shown the overall spatial pattern across the regions.

Availability of Basic Amenities in the Scheduled Castes Household

The availability of household basic amenities in Scheduled Caste household suggests that 93% of Scheduled Caste houses are electrified along with having an electric meter. However, SC households have power supply different time duration. The households getting the power supply with 12-18 hours per day and more than 18 hours per day shares 17% and 57% of the total households. The scheduled caste household having a source of water of a hand-pump, tap water, location of the source of water inside the houses and owner of the source of water constitutes 36%, 41%, 29% and 56% of the total surveyed households respectively. Moreover, Scheduled Caste households having LPG for cooking, a separate kitchen, a sanitary toilet facility without flush water and flush water and, toilet are connected with sewer line shares 37%, 20%, 56%, 3% and 49% of the total surveyed household respectively.

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

Therefore, approximately 80% of SC households having a kitchen within the house are unhealthy for family members, since 'open fires within house increases susceptibility to respiratory illness (Sithole, & Martin, 1990). Moreover, half of the total SC households have no improved sanitation facilities. As stated 'more than half the population in rural areas of the world has inaccessible to improved sanitation facilities' (WHO & UNICEF, 2008).

District level status of Scheduled Caste households' basic amenities shows that the district Bikaner has recorded the highest HBAI score with 1.60 followed by Bengaluru Rural and Kannur. On the contrary, district Murshidabad (-1.73) records the lowest level HBAI scores preceded by Rohtas and Araria. Map 3 displays that overall Scheduled Caste household in Northern states record lower level household basic amenities in comparison to Southern states. In Northern states, a total of 3 districts i.e. Bikaner and Udaipur, etc. have recorded a high level; 5 districts of Alwar and West Champaran, etc. registered medium level and remaining 12 districts of Mathura and Araria, etc. have recorded low level of HBAI index. In Southern states; 13 districts such as Ernakulam, Pune, etc. have registered high levels; 5 districts like Karwar and Vishakhapatnam, etc. show medium low level and; remaining 2 districts of Nagpur and Kalburagi have recorded low-level HBAI index.

Availability of Basic Amenities in the Upper-Caste Household

Availability of basic amenities in Upper-Caste households reveals that 100% of the total houses were electrified along with having an electric meter; 18% houses were powered with the electricity of 12-18 hours per day and; remaining 58% houses were powered with the electricity of more than 18 hours per day. The Upper-Caste household having a source of water of a hand-pump, tap water, inside the house of water source and self-owner of water source shares 34%, 53%, 72% and 91% of the total surveyed households respectively. The Upper-Caste households having LPG, separate kitchen, a sanitary toilet facility without flush water and flush water and, toilets connected with sewer drain shares 79%, 93%, 64%, 29% and 64% of the total surveyed household respectively.

The status of basic amenities in Upper-Caste households shows that the district Udaipur has recorded the highest HBAI score with 1.03 followed by Nalgonda and Aurangabad. On the other hand, district Banka (-2.06) registers the lowest level of HBAI score preceded by Samastipur and Sitapur. In

Northern states, a total of 6 districts such as Udaipur, South 24 Parganas, etc. have recorded a high level; 4 districts like Barmer, Murshidabad, etc. registered medium level and; remaining 10 districts such as Mathura and Banka, etc. have recorded low level of HBAI index. The entire 20 districts in Southern states have recorded a high-level HBAI index score. However, UP and Bihar is worst in case of availability of household basic amenities for Upper-Castes.

Discussion

The painstaking comparative analysis of housing quality for Upper-Castes and Scheduled Castes reveals that the major groups of 48% of scheduled caste households are semi-Katcha in nature, while 90% of the Upper-caste households are pucca houses in nature. Furthermore, the houses of Upper-caste having a cemented floor, cemented wall, cemented roof, and good living condition constitutes a higher proportion of the total household in comparison to Scheduled castes' households(appendix-1 and 2). Thus, it is clear that the overall housing quality of Upper-castes is far better than the scheduled castes' houses.

The spatial analysis of housing quality for both the social groups Upper-castes and scheduled castes tells that the housing quality of scheduled caste in Northern states is higher than Southern states. On the other hand, the housing quality of Upper-castes is very good across the study area, especially in Kerala, Karnataka, and Rajasthan (Map-1 and 2). Thus, it can be noted that the housing quality of Scheduled castes has a lower capacity to provide a safe and healthy environment facilitating to their family members for growth in comparison to Upper-caste households. Therefore, scheduled castes households having a relatively lower possibility of a safe and healthy environment in the family, because poor housing quality and inadequate access to material resources affects directly to health and immunity of

children and restrict what parents can do to protect children and promote their development (Leventhal & Newman, 2010).

The meticulous comparative analysis of the availability of household amenities between Upper-Castes and Scheduled Castes reveals that the availability of electricity, elect meter and time duration of power shows that both the social groups are more or less equal. Whereas, in cases of availability of tap water, location, and ownership of drinking water, LPG, location of the kitchen, sanitary toilet with and without flush connected to sewer suggest that the proportion of Upper-caste houses is much higher than the scheduled castes (Appendix-3 and 4). Thus, it is may say that there is no much dissimilarity in both social groups in the availability of common service amenities; whereas, Scheduled castes households are deprived in the availability of personal household amenities in comparison to Upper-caste households.

The spatial analysis of the availability of household basic amenities for both the social groups i.e. Upper-castes and Scheduled castes reveals that the availability of household basic amenities is more or less the same for both the social groups across the surveyed states. However, Kerala, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Maharashtra are favorable for scheduled castes household in comparison to Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, and West Bengal. Similarly, Southern states along with west Bengal are much favorable to Upper-Castes in the availability of household basic amenities (Map-3 and 4). The similar findings have been observed that the housing quality including internal facilities and external construction materials met minimum standards in half of the dwellings in developing countries (Muoghalu, 1991).

Conclusion

The conscientious spatial and comparative analysis of housing quality and availability of household basic amenities and facilities reveals

that generally, the housing quality of scheduled castes is low in comparison to Upper-castes houses. Though there is no much difference in the availability of common service amenities, scheduled castes households are deprived of the availability of personal household amenities and facilities. The Scheduled castes are considered one of the most disadvantaged social groups in Indian society that has been clearly shown true in the light of primary data in terms of spatio-comparative analysis of housing quality and availability of common basics facilities and personal household amenities between Upper-castes and Scheduled castes across India. Nonetheless, housing quality and availability of household basic amenities and facilities suffer from spatial variation for both the social groups across India. The household basic amenities in southern states are much better than southern states for both social groups. The UP and Bihar are worst for both social groups; while all the Southern states are best for Upper caste households. Thus, it can be stated that Scheduled castes' households have lower quality and lower capability to provide a healthy and comfortable household environment in comparison to their counterparts.

References

- Abdi, H. & Williams, L.J. (2010). Principal Component Analysis. Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Statistics. 2 (4): 433–459.
- Aikara, J. (1980). Scheduled castes and Higher Education: A Study of College Students in Mumbai. Pune, Ramchandra Dastane.
- Bartlett S. (1999). Children's experience of the physical environment in poor urban settlements and the implications for policy and practice. Environment & Urbanization. pp. 11:63–73.
- Chauhan, B.R. (1975). Special problems of Scheduled Castes. in M. S. Gore, et al. (ed.). Papers in the Sociology of Education in India, Delhi. NCERT.
- Collins DA, Sithole SD, Martin KS. (1990). Indoor woodsmoke pollution causing lower respiratory disease in children. Tropical Doctor. 20:151–155.

Dreze, J. and G.G. Kingdon (1999). School Participation in Rural India. LSE Development Economics Discussion Paper Series. No.18, London: London School of Economics.

Fisk WJ, Lei-Gomez Q, Mendell MJ. (2007). Meta-analysis of the associations of respiratory health effects with dampness and mold in homes. *Indoor Air*. 17:284–296.

Galanter, M. (1984). *Competing Inequalities: Law and the Backward Classes in India*. Berkely, California University Press.

Jolliffe I.T. (1986). *Principal Component Analysis and Factor Analysis*. In: *Principal Component Analysis*. Springer Series in Statistics. Springer, New York, NY.

Leventhal T, Newman S. (2010). Housing and child development. *Children and Youth Services Review*. 32:1165–1174.

Muoghalu L. (1991). Measuring housing and environmental quality as an indicator of quality of urban life: A case of traditional city of Benin, Nigeria. *Social Indicators Research*. 25:63–98.

NUEPA (2009). *Educational Development Index (EDI): a Suggestive Framework for Computation*, Department of Educational Management Information System. NUEPA, Version 2: 2009.

Robert H. Bradley and Diane L. Putnick (2012). Housing Quality and Access to Material and Learning Resources within the Home Environment in Developing Countries. *Child development*, 2012, 83 (1), 76-91.

World Health Organization and United Nations Children's Fund Joint Monitoring Programme for Water Supply and Sanitation. *Progress on drinking water and sanitation: Special focus on sanitation*. Geneva, Switzerland: WHO Press; 2008. Available online: http://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/monitoring/jmp2008.pdf.

Appendix

Appendix-1 Housing Quality of Scheduled Castes Household								
SL	District	Semi-Pucca House	Pucca House	Cemented Floor	Cemented Wall	Cemented Roof	Good Condition House	Housing Quality Index (HQI)
1	Ernakulam	27.27	72.73	90.91	81.82	72.73	36.36	-1.400
2	Thiruvananthapuram	20.00	60.00	60.00	70.00	60.00	10.00	-1.327
3	Alappuzha	45.45	45.45	54.55	54.55	27.27	0.00	0.449
4	Mallapuram	50.00	40.00	50.00	30.00	30.00	20.00	-0.687
5	Kannur	10.00	90.00	80.00	90.00	90.00	50.00	-1.595
6	Mysore	100.00	0.00	10.00	30.00	10.00	0.00	0.102
7	Bengaluru Rural	50.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	30.00	20.00	-0.918
8	Uttara Kannada	80.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	10.00	-0.109
9	Davanagere	20.00	60.00	40.00	80.00	80.00	30.00	-1.079
10	Kalburagi	80.00	0.00	0.00	50.00	50.00	0.00	-1.396
11	Anantapur	70.00	30.00	30.00	100.00	100.00	20.00	-1.104
12	SPS Nellore	90.00	10.00	10.00	70.00	50.00	10.00	0.268
13	Visakhapatnam	50.00	10.00	10.00	60.00	60.00	10.00	-0.743
14	Nalgonda	30.00	60.00	60.00	80.00	80.00	50.00	-0.847
15	Karimnagar	50.00	10.00	20.00	30.00	40.00	10.00	-1.823
16	Nagpur	70.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	-0.265
17	Latur	50.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	10.00	0.391
18	Kolhapur	80.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.596
19	Pune	20.00	30.00	40.00	30.00	50.00	30.00	0.083
20	Aurangabad	80.00	10.00	20.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	-0.865
21	Udaipur	60.00	40.00	50.00	40.00	30.00	50.00	0.562
22	Barmer	70.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	-0.681
23	Bikaner	20.00	80.00	80.00	90.00	80.00	70.00	1.876
24	Ajmer	30.00	70.00	70.00	80.00	80.00	50.00	1.131
25	Alwar	40.00	60.00	60.00	90.00	0.00	50.00	-0.073
26	Purulia	40.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	20.00	0.910
27	W. Midnapore	30.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	0.923
28	S.24 Parganas	30.00	20.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	0.942
29	Murshidabad	70.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.367
30	Jalpaiguri	20.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	-0.967
31	Araria	30.00	10.00	20.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	1.259
32	Banka	30.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	0.134
33	Samastipur	50.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	-0.144
34	W. Champaran	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	0.510
35	Rohtas	40.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.993
36	Gorakhpur	60.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	10.00	-0.555
37	Sonbhadra	45.45	36.36	36.36	36.36	0.00	36.36	0.610
38	Sitapur	30.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	2.051
39	Bijnor	50.00	30.00	10.00	20.00	0.00	10.00	1.915
40	Mathura	60.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	30.00	30.00	1.097
	Total	47.89	29.28	31.02	39.45	33.00	20.10	0.006

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

Appendix-2								
Housing Quality of Upper-Castes Household								
SL	District	Semi-Pucca House	Pucca House	Cemented Floor	Cemented Wall	Cemented Roof	Good Condition House	Housing Quality Index (HQI)
1	Ernakulam	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
2	Thiruvananthapuram	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	80.00	60.00	0.197
3	Alappuzha	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
4	Mallapuram	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
5	Kannur	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
6	Mysore	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
7	Bengaluru Rural	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
8	Uttara Kannada	20.00	80.00	100.00	100.00	60.00	100.00	-0.014
9	Davanagere	20.00	80.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	80.00	-0.072
10	Kalburagi	20.00	80.00	100.00	40.00	100.00	80.00	0.696
11	Anantapur	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	-0.807
12	SPS Nellore	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
13	Visakhapatnam	20.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	100.00	80.00	-0.590
14	Nalgonda	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
15	Karimnagar	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
16	Nagpur	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
17	Latur	20.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	-0.667
18	Kolhapur	0.00	100.00	100.00	80.00	80.00	60.00	-0.048
19	Pune	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
20	Aurangabad	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
21	Udaipur	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
22	Barmer	60.00	40.00	80.00	60.00	60.00	40.00	-2.525
23	Bikaner	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	80.00	100.00	0.619
24	Ajmer	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
25	Alwar	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.311
26	Purulia	40.00	60.00	60.00	80.00	60.00	40.00	-1.996
27	W. Midnapore	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
28	S.24 Parganas	20.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	60.00	-0.878
29	Murshidabad	0.00	100.00	100.00	80.00	100.00	100.00	0.451
30	Jalpaiguri	20.00	80.00	80.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	-0.133
31	Araria	40.00	40.00	40.00	80.00	80.00	40.00	-2.454
32	Banka	20.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	-0.667
33	Samastipur	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
34	W. Champaran	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
35	Rohtas	20.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	-0.667
36	Gorakhpur	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.311
37	Sonbhadra	20.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	0.00	60.00	-1.187
38	Sitapur	20.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	0.00	40.00	-2.957
39	Bijnor	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	60.00	100.00	0.542
40	Mathura	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.696
	Total	9.00	89.50	92.00	91.00	82.00	87.00	0.000

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

Appendix-3-A									
Availability of Basic Amenities in the Household of Scheduled Castes									
SL	District	Electricity		Power in Hours		Source of Water		Location of SW	Owner of SW
		Electricity	Elect Meter	12-18 Hrs	> 18 Hrs	Hand Pump	Tap Water	Inside	Personal
1	Ernakulam	81.82	81.82	0.00	81.82	0.00	100.00	9.09	72.73
2	Thiruvananthapuram	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	10.00	60.00	10.00	70.00
3	Alappuzha	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	72.73	9.09	100.00
4	Mallapuram	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	10.00	50.00
5	Kannur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	30.00	10.00	70.00
6	Mysore	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	70.00	90.00
7	Bengaluru Rural	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	40.00	60.00
8	Uttara Kannada	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	10.00
9	Davanagere	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	70.00	10.00	40.00
10	Kalburagi	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	60.00	30.00	10.00	50.00
11	Anantapur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	40.00	70.00
12	SPS Nellore	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	10.00	10.00
13	Visakhapatnam	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	20.00	10.00
14	Nalgonda	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	90.00	60.00	90.00
15	Karimnagar	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	80.00	0.00	10.00
16	Nagpur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	90.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
17	Latur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	40.00	40.00
18	Kolhapur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	60.00	10.00	30.00
19	Pune	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	40.00	40.00
20	Aurangabad	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
21	Udaipur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	60.00	50.00
22	Barmer	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	50.00	10.00	70.00	70.00
23	Bikaner	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	90.00	80.00
24	Ajmer	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	70.00	90.00
25	Alwar	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	30.00	50.00	50.00
26	Purulia	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	80.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
27	W. Midnapore	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
28	S.24 Parganas	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	10.00	90.00	10.00	0.00
29	Murshidabad	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	10.00	100.00
30	Jalpaiguri	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
31	Araria	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	30.00	90.00
32	Banka	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	20.00	40.00
33	Samastipur	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	20.00	100.00
34	W. Champaran	80.00	80.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	30.00	80.00
35	Rohtas	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	50.00	90.00
36	Gorakhpur	80.00	60.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	20.00	100.00
37	Sonbhadra	90.91	90.91	90.91	0.00	100.00	0.00	36.36	63.64
38	Sitapur	20.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
39	Bijnor	90.00	90.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	90.00	100.00
40	Mathura	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	90.00	100.00
	Total	93.80	93.30	17.37	57.07	35.73	41.44	28.78	55.83

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

Appendix-3-B							
Availability of Basic Amenities in the Household of Scheduled Castes							
SL	District	Cooking Fuel	Location of Kitchen	Toilet Facility & Its Connection			Household Basic Amenity Index (HBAI)
		LPG	Separate	Sanitary without Flush	Sanitary with Flush	Sever	
1	Ernakulam	72.73	54.55	81.82	9.09	63.64	1.404
2	Thiruvananthapuram	70.00	20.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.749
3	Alappuzha	63.64	45.45	90.91	9.09	90.91	1.072
4	Mallapuram	30.00	20.00	90.00	10.00	100.00	0.545
5	Kannur	70.00	60.00	70.00	30.00	100.00	1.413
6	Mysore	100.00	0.00	90.00	0.00	100.00	0.979
7	Bengaluru Rural	90.00	30.00	70.00	10.00	80.00	1.446
8	Uttara Kannada	50.00	10.00	80.00	0.00	90.00	0.217
9	Davanagere	70.00	20.00	80.00	0.00	100.00	0.800
10	Kalburagi	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	-1.122
11	Anantapur	80.00	10.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	1.003
12	SPS Nellore	50.00	10.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	1.139
13	Visakhapatnam	30.00	10.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.436
14	Nalgonda	80.00	40.00	90.00	10.00	100.00	1.340
15	Karimnagar	30.00	20.00	40.00	0.00	40.00	0.033
16	Nagpur	10.00	20.00	20.00	10.00	30.00	-0.863
17	Latur	40.00	30.00	70.00	0.00	70.00	0.616
18	Kolhapur	40.00	10.00	60.00	0.00	60.00	0.107
19	Pune	60.00	30.00	60.00	20.00	80.00	1.149
20	Aurangabad	10.00	10.00	90.00	0.00	90.00	-0.035
21	Udaipur	50.00	40.00	80.00	0.00	80.00	0.885
22	Barmer	40.00	10.00	60.00	0.00	70.00	-0.338
23	Bikaner	90.00	90.00	100.00	0.00	60.00	1.590
24	Ajmer	30.00	30.00	70.00	0.00	70.00	0.751
25	Alwar	80.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.195
26	Purulia	10.00	20.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	-1.198
27	W. Midnapore	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	10.00	-0.923
28	S.24 Parganas	0.00	10.00	60.00	0.00	20.00	0.047
29	Murshidabad	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	-1.732
30	Jalpaiguri	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	10.00	-1.129
31	Araria	10.00	10.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	-1.298
32	Banka	0.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	-0.539
33	Samastipur	0.00	20.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	-1.103
34	W. Champaran	50.00	30.00	80.00	0.00	0.00	-0.384
35	Rohtas	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	-1.621
36	Gorakhpur	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	-1.290
37	Sonbhadra	0.00	18.18	9.09	0.00	0.00	-1.156
38	Sitapur	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.739
39	Bijnor	0.00	0.00	60.00	0.00	0.00	-1.210
40	Mathura	20.00	30.00	70.00	0.00	0.00	-0.848
	Total	36.72	20.35	56.82	2.73	48.64	0.003

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

Appendix-4-A Availability of Basic Amenities in the Household of Upper-Castes									
SL	District	Electricity		Power in Hours		Source of Water		Location & Owner: Source of Water	
		Electricity	Elect Meter	12-18 Hrs	> 18 Hrs	Hand Pump	Tap Water	Inside	Personal
1	Ernakulam	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
2	Thiruvananthapuram	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	80.00	40.00	100.00
3	Alappuzha	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
4	Mallapuram	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
5	Kannur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	80.00	60.00	100.00
6	Mysore	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
7	Bengaluru Rural	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	80.00	100.00
8	Uttara Kannada	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	60.00	60.00	100.00
9	Davanagere	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	40.00	80.00
10	Kalburagi	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	60.00	100.00
11	Anantapur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	80.00	100.00
12	SPS Nellore	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
13	Visakhapatnam	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	40.00
14	Nalgonda	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	80.00	100.00
15	Karimnagar	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	20.00	60.00	40.00	100.00
16	Nagpur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	20.00	80.00	100.00	100.00
17	Latur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	80.00	80.00
18	Kolhapur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	80.00	100.00
19	Pune	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
20	Aurangabad	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	80.00	100.00
21	Udaipur	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	80.00
22	Barmer	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	20.00	60.00	80.00
23	Bikaner	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Appendix-4-B							
Availability of Basic Amenities in the Household of Upper-Castes							
SL	District	Cooking Fuel	Location of Kitchen	Toilet Facility & Its Connection			Household Basic Amenity Index (HBAI)
		LPG	Separate	Sanitary without Flush	Sanitary with flush	Sever	
1	Ernakulam	100.00	100.00	40.00	60.00	80.00	0.739
2	Thiruvananthapuram	100.00	100.00	40.00	60.00	100.00	0.915
3	Alappuzha	100.00	100.00	60.00	40.00	80.00	0.768
4	Mallapuram	80.00	100.00	20.00	80.00	100.00	0.300
5	Kannur	100.00	100.00	60.00	40.00	100.00	0.890
6	Mysore	100.00	100.00	40.00	60.00	100.00	0.863
7	Bengaluru Rural	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.240
8	Uttara Kannada	100.00	100.00	60.00	40.00	100.00	0.783
9	Davanagere	100.00	100.00	40.00	60.00	100.00	0.437
10	Kalburagi	60.00	100.00	80.00	20.00	100.00	0.927
11	Anantapur	100.00	80.00	80.00	20.00	100.00	0.766
12	SPS Nellore	100.00	100.00	20.00	80.00	100.00	0.396
13	Visakhapatnam	100.00	80.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.377
14	Nalgonda	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	1.001
15	Karimnagar	100.00	100.00	60.00	40.00	100.00	0.717
16	Nagpur	100.00	100.00	60.00	40.00	100.00	0.664
17	Latur	80.00	80.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.966
18	Kolhapur	80.00	80.00	60.00	40.00	100.00	0.768
19	Pune	100.00	100.00	20.00	80.00	100.00	0.834
20	Aurangabad	100.00	100.00	80.00	20.00	100.00	0.973
21	Udaipur	100.00	100.00	60.00	40.00	100.00	1.032
22	Barmer	20.00	80.00	20.00	0.00	20.00	-0.478
23	Bikaner	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	60.00	0.701
24	Ajmer	80.00	100.00	80.00	20.00	100.00	0.492
25	Alwar	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.437
26	Purulia	80.00	80.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.359
27	W. Midnapore	80.00	100.00	80.00	20.00	100.00	0.629
28	S.24 Parganas	80.00	80.00	60.00	40.00	0.00	0.210
29	Murshidabad	100.00	100.00	60.00	40.00	0.00	-0.808
30	Jalpaiguri	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	40.00	-0.277
31	Araria	60.00	80.00	60.00	40.00	0.00	-1.357
32	Banka	20.00	80.00	80.00	0.00	0.00	-2.064
33	Samastipur	20.00	60.00	80.00	0.00	0.00	-1.687
34	W. Champaran	20.00	80.00	60.00	40.00	40.00	-1.477
35	Rohtas	40.00	100.00	60.00	40.00	20.00	-1.532
36	Gorakhpur	60.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	-1.415
37	Sonbhadra	80.00	100.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	-1.514
38	Sitapur	0.00	60.00	60.00	0.00	0.00	-1.653
39	Bijnor	60.00	80.00	60.00	40.00	0.00	-1.571
40	Mathura	40.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	-1.479
	Total	78.50	92.50	63.50	28.50	63.50	0.000

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015